

Overtake Behavior Model of Motorcycle on Accident Risk

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Abstract

The imbalance of transportation facilities and infrastructure, resulting in traffic jams and poor driver's aggressive behavior, especially in overtaking vehicles in front of them, cause an accident. The study's purpose is to analyze the behavior characteristics of overtaking motorcycle, test and analyze the relationship model between accident risk and motorcycle behavior and determine strategic step recommendations to reduce accidents risk to realize safety riding in Makassar City. Data collection methods used to achieve targets and study outcomes are observation, documentation, and literature review. Related statistical methods analyzed data. The variable explained is the motorcycle behavior related to driver ability to maintain a safe distance in the longitudinal and lateral directions. The results indicate a relationship between motorcycle rider behavior and accident frequency. Based on the longitudinal direction, it is known that the greater vehicle distance, the smaller accidents risk arising with a safe distance of 4.62 meters. Meanwhile, in the lateral direction, it is known that the greater distance between vehicles will increase accident risk. The safe distance between vehicles in the lateral direction is 1.88 meters.

Keywords: *Traffic accidents, motorcycle, driver behavior*

1. Introduction

The rapid development of vehicles that are not comparable with urban transportation facilities and infrastructure impacts on congestion, environmental pollution, fuel consumption, land consumption, as well as security and public order issues [1]. Besides, security and public order problems caused by uncontrolled vehicle growth and inadequate transportation systems will lead to high accident rates [1].

There are four factors causing transportation accidents in Indonesia: the condition of transportation infrastructure, and human and natural factors. However, among these four factors, human negligence is the main factor causing the high number of traffic accidents [2], [3]. Data shows that traffic accidents are triggered by human error, road, and environmental facilities, vehicles, and traffic signs [4-6].

One of the aggressive behavior of other riders is to maneuver zig-zag in overtaking vehicles. The riders do not use the same lane but will make use of the space between the vehicles, especially the motorbike riders that cause congruence in traffic. This condition reflects heterogeneous traffic patterns, which can lead to high accident risk. It is worsened by the increasing uncontrolled vehicle volume, causing the distance between vehicles to be smaller, which can increase traffic accidents risk. Heterogeneous traffic conditions where vehicles spillover on the road without distinguishing vehicle characteristics and functions will be easily found in Makassar City [7-10].

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For this reason, more attention needs to be paid to traffic safety, which leads to partial accident mitigation involving traffic control and management strategies to increase the level of safety riding. Based on the description, this study examines the relationship between accident risk and overtaking behavior of motorcycle to obtain an appropriate model of accident risk and mitigation to reduce accident rates in Makassar City. This study also examines the behavior of motorcyclists in overtaking vehicles on the highway as an integral part of an accident. Therefore, the purpose of this study was to analyze the behavior characteristics of overtaking motorcycle vehicles in Makassar City to test and analyze the relationship model of accident risk and motorcycle rider behavior.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Definition of Traffic Accidents

In the Republic of Indonesia Law No. 22 of 2009 Article 1 number 24 concerning traffic and road transportation that a traffic accident is an unexpected and unintentional road event involving vehicles with or without other road users resulting in human casualties and property losses [11]. Road traffic accidents can be defined as accidents occurring on a public traffic road, resulting in one or more people being killed or injured, and at least one moving vehicle involved. Therefore, road accidents are collisions between vehicles, vehicles and pedestrians, vehicles and animals, or between vehicles and geographical or architectural obstacles.

The General Plan of Road Transportation Safety (2006) also outlined the leading causes of a traffic accident affected by human factors, vehicles, and road environments, as well as the interaction and combination of two or more of the factors mentioned above. It can be seen from Figure 1 [12].

Figure 1. Factors that cause accidents and their interactions

2.2. Characteristics of Rider Behavior

Behavior is a statement of activities that others can observe and is the result of a combination of understanding external influences and internal influences. Traffic problems can be caused by factors and, most importantly, human factors as road users, both as drivers and pedestrians in general. While the discipline and legal awareness of

road user communities still cannot be said to be good, do not yet have compliance, obedience to follow applicable laws [13].

2.2.1. Aggressive Driving

Driving aggression occurs when drivers have difficulty controlling their emotions when they are driving. Factors of driving aggressive behavior are mood, age and gender, personality, lifestyle, driver's attitude, and intention [14]. While some external causes are noise, temperature, overcrowding, and territoriality, this life phenomenon is often found in big cities as a metropolis as a cause of the external impacts of complex problems.

Other studies suggest that teenage motorists are known for their anxious driving behaviors, such as speeding, trailing other vehicles too close, and running red lights. These behaviors are aggressive driving behaviors, namely driving behavior that is done intentionally, tends to increase the risk of collisions, and is motivated by impatience, resentment, hostility, and or efforts to save time [15]. Aggressive driving behavior stems from the perception of accident risk in adolescents. The perception of accident risk is a subjective assessment of an accident's occurrence and how much individual attention will be the consequences [16].

2.2.2. Preparing Behavior

In the kinematic characteristic of a vehicle is the ability to move a vehicle without considering the forces that cause the movement. The main element in vehicle kinematic characteristics is the ability of the vehicle to accelerate. Vehicle acceleration is influenced by several factors, including movement to prepare, gap acceptance, and size of the prepared lane [17]. The movement includes several stages of acceleration. First, the acceleration to approach the vehicle to be prepared. Second, the acceleration aligns with the prepared vehicle. Third, the acceleration to return to the original lane and place it in front of the ready vehicle. Gap acceptance is a decision that must be taken by motorists and pedestrians. This decision is strongly influenced by the time of the driver's perception-reaction; gap acceptance is also very dependent on the vehicle's ability to accelerate [18].

2.3. Relationship Between Preparing and Traffic Flow

From several studies relating to the behavior of preparing with the characteristics of traffic flow. As a study of overtaking behavior among motorcycle users [19], exploring the attributes for driving motorbike movements to pass with a safe distance is based on the assumption that the motorcycle is trying to maintain a safe distance during overtaking. This study concludes that with high traffic density, the safe distance will be smaller. It means that accident rates can quickly occur. Another thing was found that 92.5% of motorists received a risk of collision when overtaking, and 62% of exceeding might cause a traffic accident.

Vogel (2003), tries to compare headway with accident time as an indicator of accidents [20] conducted a study that examined the relationship of overtaking characteristics with service levels in heterogeneous traffic. The same was done by Minh et al. [21], researching overtaking behavior for motorcycle riders. Some of the variables collected are vehicle speed, transverse distance, and lengthwise between overtaking vehicles. The overtaking behavior for motorcyclists has also been investigated by Mocsari [22] to determine the relationship between average overtaking speed and acceleration.

2.4. Accident Identification

Identification of accident-prone traffic locations provides a requirement for determining the worst accident location or which has the highest priority to get treatment. The identification of accident-prone traffic areas includes two stages, including accident

history from the entire study area, studied to select several locations that are prone to accidents, and selected locations studied in detail to find the treatment carried out. In identifying accidents, Lai [23] conducted an assessment of accident risk, accident rates, death rates, injury rates, and death rates/injuries that were indexed for evaluation. The accident rate and casualty rate of each road section are revealed by the number of accidents and the number of victims per million kilometers traveled by the vehicle.

$$\text{Accident rate} = \text{Number of accidents} / (\text{Number of vehicles} \times \text{road length}/1,000,000) \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Death rate} = \text{Number of deaths} / (\text{Number of vehicles} * \text{road length}/1,000,000) \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Injury rate} = \text{Number of injuries} / (\text{Number of vehicles} * \text{road length}/1,000,000) \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Victim rate} = \text{Number of victims} / (\text{Number of vehicles} * \text{road length}/1,000,000) \quad (4)$$

2.5. Accident Modeling Concepts with Generalized Linear Modelling (GLM)

The approach concept to predict accident uses a conventional linear regression approach, namely, assuming normally distributed data. Although the model statistically significant results from accident modeling, it cannot accurately represent the distribution of accident data, especially the time and place of the incident. Therefore, to form a model with observational data (response variables) that are not normally distributed, another form is used, namely Generalized Linear Modeling (GLM). Accident models on-road sections using the Generalized Linear Modeling model format as follows [24].

$$Y = kQ^\alpha \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

$$Y = kQ^\alpha e^{b_1g_1+b_2g_2+\dots} \dots\dots\dots (6)$$

Where:

Y: Accident Rate

Q: Traffic Volume

g_1, g_2 : Driver behavior variable

α, k, b_1, b_2 : estimated parameter

3. Methodology of Research

In this study, for data retrieval related to behavioral characteristics and microscopic characteristics of traffic flow, and carried out in the following way.

3.1. Driver Behavior and Microscopic Characteristics of Traffic Flow Data

This data is primary data that was conducted using a direct survey method on several roads based on the highest accident frequency that occurred in Makassar City. This data records the number of motorbikes that overtaking or overtaking other vehicles. This data was obtained using a Closed Circuit Television (CCTV) recorder placed at a certain height that did not disturb the traffic flow, visibility, and driver concentration. The recording process is carried out for a week and is carried out from 06.00 - 22.00. A recording device can be mounted on a crossing bridge, fly over, or use a specific method to place the camera at an elevation.

3.2. Determining the Gap of the Vehicle Preparing Process

Primary data of recordings (video) are played back to be evaluated and to get the desired data in tables or graphs form. There are three stages of the driver's behavior during the preparation process: preparation, preparation, and after preparation. The next data processing procedure is the grid method. This method is to make a road grid from

transparent paper or plastic so that the area is the same as the monitor or television screen used to display the recording process. Paper or plastic grids are made according to the road distance and width divided into the same size segments. The grid method is used for the gap between vehicles from the lateral and longitudinal directions during the preparation process. This method is also used to get the travel time during the preparation process.

4. Results and Discussion

This study collects accident data from the Makassar City Resort Police in the 2015 - 2019 period. The description of accidents in the last five years, as shown in Figure 2. This Figure illustrates that the accident rate has increased significantly over the past five years.

Figure 2. Number of Traffic Accidents in the 2015 – 2019 Period

The average accident that occurs for five years is 1,238. Traffic accidents in Makassar City are dominated by motorcycle users, with the proportion reaching 64.35%. The average accident was 2.7 accidents/day, and the average number of victims of motorcycle users was 3.3 people/day. The proportion of motorcycle accidents occur on working days by 79.25%, with an incident occurring predominantly in the morning at 33.77%. The majority of motorcycle users involved in male accidents were 72.85%. Generally, it occurs in the productive age range, i.e., 18-55 years, with a percentage reaching 71.89%.

4.1. Traffic, Geometric and Driver Behavior Characteristics

Accident-prone areas in Makassar are found in three roads are *Perintis Kemerdekaan* Street, *Urip Sumiharjo* Street, and *A.P. Pettarani* Street. In the model's formation analysis, the three roads are divided into several segments with almost identical geometric conditions and traffic characteristics. The three road segments are divided into ten road segments, namely, on *Perintis Kemerdekaan* street into six road segments, *Urip Sumiharjo* street into two road segments, and *A.P. Pettarani* street into two road segments. These ten road segments serve as study objects—the division of the ten road segments, as described in Table 1.

Table 1. Road Segments and Accident Frequency

Road Names	Road Segments	Accident Frequency
<i>Perintis Kemerdekaan</i>	<i>PLTU – BTP</i>	38
	<i>BTP – Telkomas</i>	9
	<i>Telkomas - Daya</i>	11
	<i>Daya - Baddoka</i>	33
	<i>Baddoka – Goaria</i>	21
	<i>Goaria – Simpang 5</i>	11
<i>Urip Sumiharjo</i>	<i>PLTU – Fly Over</i>	35
	<i>Fly Over – M. Raya</i>	30
<i>A.P. Pettarani</i>	<i>S.Alauddin - Boulevard</i>	10
	<i>Boulevard – Fly Over</i>	37

Accident data is taken from January 2015 to December 2019. The data show that the highest accident segment occurred in the PLTU-BTP segment on *Perintis Kemerdekaan* Street with an accident frequency of 38 per year. While on the *Urip Sumiharjo* Street segment occurred in the PLTU-Flyover with accident frequency of 35 per year and 37 accidents per year occur on the Boulevard-Flyover segment on *A.P. Pettarani* Street.

4.2. Traffic Flow and Geometric Characteristics of the Road

Traffic flow and geometric characteristics of the road reviewed as study objects include traffic volume, speed, road length, and road type. The average volume of each road segment shows that the highest average volume occurs on *Perintis Kemerdekaan* Street, *Urip Sumiharjo* Street, and *A.P. Pettarani* Street were 9,006 vehicles per hour, 4,340 vehicles per hour, and 7,959 vehicles per hour, respectively. These three most significant volumes occur in the road segment between the PLTU-BTP intersection, *Masjid Raya*-Flyover intersection, and between the Flyover-Boulevard junction. Related data about motorcycle speed are analyzed by statistical parameters, namely the average speed of each road segment.

Speed data collected from 100 vehicles for each type of vehicle for every hour in the 06.00-21.00 period. The average motorbike speed is 36.5 km/hour. Other variables related to traffic accident modeling that will be included in model formation analysis are geometric road variables. The results of characteristics identifying each road segment are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Traffic and Road Geometric Characteristics

Road Segment	LHR	Speed	Segment length	Road Type
<i>PLTU – BTP</i>	9.006	38,7	3.780	8/2 D
<i>BTP – Telkomas</i>	8.486	31,4	1.360	8/2 D
<i>Telkomas - Daya</i>	5.533	30,5	1.390	6/2 D
<i>Daya - Baddoka</i>	3.428	36,9	2.100	6/2 UD
<i>Baddoka – Goaria</i>	3.416	41,3	2.150	6/2 UD
<i>Goaria – Simpang 5</i>	3.303	35,2	1.110	6/2 UD
<i>PLTU – Fly Over</i>	4.041	34,7	3.480	6/2 D
<i>Fly Over – M. Raya</i>	4.341	33,0	2.510	6/2 D
<i>S. Alauddin - Boulevard</i>	7.959	34,3	2.190	6/2 D
<i>Boulevard – Fly Over</i>	7.529	35,6	2.150	6/2 D

Table 2 shows that the geometric characteristics of the *Perintis Kemerdekaan* Street have a higher road longer than the two other road segments. The length of the *Perintis Kemerdekaan* Street of 11.890 km, with an average width of the road benefit ranging

from 22.08 m, whereas *Urip Sumiharjo* Street has a road length of 5.99 km with an average width of 21.86 m. *A.P. Pettarani* Street has a greater width of road benefits than the other two road segments. This road has an average road benefit width of 42.99 m with a road length of 4.34 km.

4.3. Characteristics of Rider Behavior

Characteristics of motorist behavior that are made as the object of study are the following behavior and lateral behavior. This behavior shows how the driver maintains a safe distance between the vehicle he is driving with other vehicles. For that, the measured driver behavior is the longitudinal distance and lateral distance between vehicles. As shown in Table 3, longitudinal and lateral distances from each road segment are known from the results of data processing. The longitudinal distance between the most massive vehicles occurs on *Perintis Kemerdekaan* Street in *Goaria* intersection-*Simpang 5* intersection, which is 2.10 m. Whereas the lateral distance occurs on *A.P. Pettarani* Street in *Boulevard-Fly Over* segment, which is 1.45 m. All of these results are correlated with the accident rate accompanied by other supporting variables, namely traffic volume, speed, and road geometry, for driver behavior model formation towards traffic accidents risk. The characteristics of the driver's behavior are related to the longitudinal distance and lateral distance, as shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Longitudinal and Lateral Distance from the Rider's Behavior

Road Segment	Distance	
	longitudinal	lateral
<i>PLTU – BTP</i>	0,90	1,00
<i>BTP – Telkomas</i>	0,40	0,40
<i>Telkomas – Daya</i>	0,85	0,60
<i>Daya – Baddoka</i>	0,75	0,45
<i>Baddoka – Goaria</i>	1,25	0,85
<i>Goaria – Simpang 5</i>	2,10	1,00
<i>PLTU – Fly Over</i>	0,95	0,95
<i>Fly Over – M. Raya</i>	0,85	0,45
<i>S. Alauddin - Boulevard</i>	1,35	0,95
<i>Boulevard – Fly Over</i>	1,45	1,45

4.4. Modeling of Motorcycle Rider Behavior Towards Accident Risk

Analysis modeling was conducted using GLM (Generalized Linear Modeling). This method uses the Poisson distribution and its logarithmic link function. The level of significance and dispersion is set at 5% as a criterion for the model estimation process. The GLM model was created to determine the relationship between accident risk and the behavior of motorcycle riders concerning the following behavior and lateral behavior. The following behavior is the distance between two vehicles in the longitudinal direction, while the lateral behavior is the distance between two vehicles in the lateral direction.

The model analysis results in predicting accident frequency and significance figures for Univariate analysis to see each explanatory variable (vehicle volume, speed, longitudinal distance, and lateral distance) on the response variable (accident frequency). Multivariate analysis to see the effect of explanatory variables together on the response variable. GLM analysis results are as in Table 4.

Table 4. Longitudinal and Lateral Distance from the Rider's Behavior

Parameter	B	Std. Error	95% Wald Confidence Interval	Hypothesis Test
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			Lower	Upper	Wald Chi-Square	df	Sig.
(Intercept)	2,100	,8486	,437	3,763	6,124	1	,013
Flow	,000116	3,8127E-5	,000	-4,130E-5	9,261	1	,002
Longitudinal	-1,352	,2938	-1,928	-,776	21,175	1	,000
Lateral	1,699	,3574	,998	2,399	22,586	1	,000
Speed	,049	,0227	,004	,094	4,647	1	,031
(Scale)	1 ^a						

Univariate analysis is used to see each explanatory variable (vehicle volume, speed, longitudinal distance, and lateral distance) on the response variable (accident frequency). Univariate analysis was obtained using the t-test, and the results can be seen in Table 4. Based on Table 4, it can be seen that the vehicle volume p-value is 0.002. This value is higher than the alpha (α) value of 0.05. Thus it can be concluded that the volume of vehicles significantly influences the frequency of accidents. The same condition of longitudinal distances, given the significant level produced at 0,000, is smaller than the α value, which is equal to 0.05. These results indicate that the longitudinal length affects the frequency of accidents.

Meanwhile, the lateral distance variable shows the same as longitudinal distance, where the significance value produced is 0,000 or smaller than the α value, which is equal to 0.05. Therefore, it is known that lateral distance affects accident frequency. Besides, the speed variable has significant value generated from the calculation results is 0.031, or the value is smaller than the α value, which is 0.05. Thus the variable speed of the motorcycle also affects the frequency of accidents.

Multivariate analysis was used to determine the effect of all explanatory variables together on the response variable—the results of the multivariate analysis using the ANOVA test, as shown in Table 5.

Table 5. ANOVA Test Results

Likelihood Ratio Chi-Square	df	Sig.
37,805	4	,000

Table 5 shows that the p-value in the multivariate analysis was 0,000. The p-value is more significant than the α in the amount of 0.05. Thus, it can be said that vehicle volume, longitudinal distance, lateral distance, and speed together significantly influence the frequency of accidents in Makassar City with a confidence level of 95%. As discussed previously, the model approach that will be used in this study uses the GLM (Generalized Linear Modeling) method. The mathematical equation model of this method is illustrated in equation (5). The results of the analysis shown in Table 4 show that the four variables produce the estimated parameter values of each variable. Generally, the constants generated from this model are 2,100 or antilog (2,100) = 8,11642. The regression coefficient for each variable is for the traffic volume variable of -0,000116, for the longitudinal distance variable -1,352, while for the lateral distance variable amounted to 1,699 and for speed of 0.049. Therefore, the traffic accident model in Makassar City forms the following mathematical equation (7).

$$TK = 8,11642.F^{-0,000116}.e^{-1,352.Lo+1,699.La+0,049.v} \dots\dots\dots (7)$$

Where:

- TK = Accident Frequency
- F = vehicle Volume (Vehicle/Hour)
- Lo = Longitudinal Distance (m)

La = Lateral Distance (m)
 V = Speed (km/h)

4.5. Model Validation and Interpretation

Based on the resulting model, it is necessary to examine the model, whether it can be used to predict motorcycle accidents in Makassar City. The first examination is carried out by comparing the accident frequency from the explanatory variable (X) with the accident frequency generated from the model formed using the paired t-test statistical method (Paired Sample t-test). This test aims to determine whether TK_{Actual} and TK_{Predicted} significantly different or not. If it is significantly different, then the resulting model cannot be used to predict motorcycle accidents. For this reason, the hypothesis of the t-test as equation (8) and (9), while paired t-test results are as shown in Table 6.

$$H_0: \mu_1 = \mu_2 \text{ or } \mu_1 - \mu_2 = 0 \dots\dots\dots (8)$$

It means that there is no real difference between the average TK_{Actual} and TK_{Predicted}.

$$H_0: \mu_1 \neq \mu_2 \text{ or } \mu_1 - \mu_2 \neq 0 \dots\dots\dots (9)$$

It means that there are real differences between the average TK_{Actual} and TK_{Predicted}.

Table 6. The paired t-test between TK_{actual} with TK_{Predict}

T-Test: Paired Two Sample for Means	Variable 1	Variable 2
Mean	23,5	46,82559
Variance	152,0555556	519,4937
Observations	10	10
Pearson Correlation	0,699344896	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	9	
t Stat	-4,420448658	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0,00083505	
t Critical one-tail	1,833112933	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0,0016701	
t Critical two-tail	2,262157163	

For decision making is to compare the value of t_{count} with t_{table}. Ho is accepted if the calculated statistics are smaller than the table statistics or vice versa rejected if the calculated statistics are higher than the table statistics. With n (total data) of 10, the degree of freedom = 9. Then the value of the t_{table} is known to be 1.8331. From Table 6, it is known that the t_{count} smaller than the t_{table} (0.0016701 < 1.8331). The results show that TK_{actual} and TK_{predicted} were not significantly different or almost the same as the 95% confidence level. These results indicate that a good model is used to predict the frequency of accidents in Makassar City.

The model interpretation is used to predict a safe distance between vehicles both in the longitudinal and lateral direction. The distance predicting assumed that all variables to be constant calculated variables—the interpretation of the longitudinal and lateral direction models, as seen in Figures 3 and 4. Figure 3 shows the relationship between accident frequency and longitudinal distance. This graph is obtained by substituting certain distances in the longitudinal direction into the GLM model and assuming other variables to have a constant value. Based on Figure 3, also known that farther vehicle distance, the accident frequency decrease. By using an exponential equation to form a trendline, an equation will be established. From the curve equation, as shown in Figure 3, the safe distance between vehicles from the longitudinal direction is when the zero accident frequency is 4.62 meters.

Figure 3. Relationship between Accident Frequency and Longitudinal Distance

Figure 4. Relationship between Accident Frequency and Lateral Distance

The same thing is shown in lateral distances model interpretation. By substituting lateral distance values ranging from 0.5 to 5 meters into the GLM model and other explanatory variables are considered constant, then we will get the predicted frequency of accident, as shown in Figure 4. Based on Figure 4, it can be seen that increasing distance between vehicles lateral direction will increase accident frequency in Makassar City. It can occur because the motorcycle rider behavior tends to fill the empty spaces between vehicles without regard to the accident risk they will cause. It was using an exponential equation to know that the safe distance between vehicles in the lateral direction is 1.88 meters.

5. Conclusion

Based on the analysis results, it can be concluded that the driver's behavior affects the accident frequency. The intended driver's behavior is maintaining a safe distance between the vehicle's longitudinal direction (following behavior) and lateral direction (lateral behavior). The GLM analysis results that form the equation $TK = 8,11642.F - 0,000116.e - 1,352.Lo + 1,699.La + 0,049.v$. Based on the equation, it is known that the longer vehicle distance, the accident frequency decrease. However, different things in the lateral distance, the longer vehicle distance cause the accident risk increasing. Therefore, the safe distance between vehicles is 4.62 meters in the longitudinal direction and 1.88 meters in the lateral direction.

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